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Report on outstanding open questions and prioritized R&D guidelines for Energy Recovery Linacs

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ABSTRACT

Energy Recovery linacs (ERLs) are a class of electron accelerators which could achieve extremely high beam intensities at moderate operating costs by recovering the beam energy, i.e. the energy of the accelerated particles, after their experimental use. The future pathway goes towards multi MW facilities, calling for the establishment of the technology required for stable high current operation. Some smaller ERLs are already in existence. Further research is needed on the following topics: ERL operation, beam dynamics, injectors, Superconducting Radiofrequency (SRF) systems and ERL applications.

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Executive summary

Energy Recovery linacs (ERLs) are a class of electron accelerators which hold the promise to achieve extremely high beam intensities at moderate operating costs by recovering the beam energy, i.e. the energy of the accelerated particles, after their experimental use. The future pathway goes to multi MW facilities, calling the establishment of the technology required for stable high current operation. Some smaller ERLs are already in existence. Further research is needed on the following topics: ERL operation, beam dynamics, injectors, SRF and ERL applications.

For advancing ERL operation, the existing and near future machines need to be run to their limits in order to gain experience, in particular, with multi-turn operation at very high beam current.

Beam dynamics issues primarily concern the coherent synchrotron radiation (CSR) and microbunching instabilities as well as the treatment of beam halo.

Injectors for ERLs need to provide very high beam current and bunch charges at high repetition rate (sometimes even cw). In this respect, cathode materials and gun design need to be further developed.

SRF in ERLs concentrates on the cw operation at medium gradients, where quality factor and efficient HOM damping are important issues. Operation at high loaded-Q values renders the machines even more energy efficient, as less RF forward power is needed. But this operation mode poses challenges in terms of RF control.

ERL applications cover a wide range, extending from photon production to direct electron scattering in particle and nuclear physics. As ERL technology becomes more mature and more firmly established, it could be exploited for additional fields, including industrial applications.

1. Introduction

Electron linear accelerators with the possibility to regain the beam energy after the experimental use – so called Energy-Recovery LINACs (ERLs) – have the potential of providing very high beam power in continuous-wave (CW) operation at moderate operational costs. At the same time, every bunch is used at the experiment only once and beam quality reduction due to the experiment is much less of an issue than, e.g., in storage rings where each bunch passes the experiment multiple times. Thereby, high-current ERLs promise to advance the fields of nuclear physics, particle physics, and sciences at advanced light sources. The layout of ERLs is always similar using recirculating linacs allowing for multiple passes through the – ideally superconducting – accelerating cavities. After the experimental use of the fully accelerated beam, e.g., in collisions with an internal target or with another beam, the electrons are decelerated in the linacs, so that their kinetic energy is transferred back to the radio-frequency (RF) fields in the accelerating/decelerating cavities. The recovery of the beam energy can yield a very high energy efficiency of ERLs, as only the injection energy (usually a few MeV) cannot be recovered and needs to be provided by the RF senders.

The concept of energy recovery in superconducting cavities was proposed by Maury Tigner in 1965 [1]. More than 20 years later it was demonstrated experimentally at Stanford [2]. The first user

facilities based on the ERL concept, e.g. an FEL photon source, were realized at JLAB [3], achieving a recovery efficiency of 99% at 150 MeV and 10 mA [4] or 98% at 1 GeV and 100 μ A [5]. End 2019 the CBETA project at Cornell university succeeded in proving, for the first time, a multi-turn ERL operation with SRF cavities, which represents a major technological step in the ERL field [6].

Currently, four ERL facilities (more details in [7]) are in operation worldwide, one of which is running with normal conducting cavities, and several ERL projects are under development. The technological goals are defined by the need of future high-current machines (>100 mA), amounting to multi MW of beam power. Challenges are encountered, in particular, in the areas of electron beam dynamics, beam diagnostics, SRF technology and electron sources.

2. State of the art and research goals in ERL science

The main research guidelines of the field are being discussed by the community in the frame of the bi-annual ICFA Advanced Beam Dynamics Workshops on Energy Recovery Linacs. The last workshop of this series was held at HZB, Berlin, Germany in September 2019. The scientific program was subdivided into five working groups: ERL facilities (WG1), ERL beam dynamics and instrumentation (WG2), Electron sources and injectors (WG3), Superconducting RF (WG4) and ERL applications (WG5). The structure of this report will follow the same classification, which well covers the main research goals of the ERL field.

2.1 ERL FACILITIES

At present only four ERL facilities are in operation worldwide [8]:

- Novosibirsk ERL at BINP in Russia (normalconducting, multi-turn) [9]
- cERL at KEK in Japan (superconducting, single-turn) [10]
- S-DALINAC ERL at TU Darmstadt in Germany (superconducting, multi-turn) [11]
- CBETA at Cornell in USA (superconducting, multi-turn) [12]

The Novosibirsk ERL is operated in multi-turn mode. It was the first multi-turn ERL world-wide. For the important family of superconducting ERLs, multi-turn ERL operation could be achieved for the first time at CBETA (Cornell) [6]. The layout of the S-DALINAC (TU Darmstadt) would also allow a multi-turn operation, but so far the S-DALINAC could be operated in single-turn ERL mode only [13].

Two more facilities are under construction currently:

- bERLinPro at HZB Berlin in Germany (superconducting, single-turn) [14]
- MESA at Johannes-Gutenberg Universität Mainz in Germany (superconducting, multi-turn) [15]

bERLinPro is planned as an accelerator test facility and envisages a cw beam current of 100 mA, while MESA will be operated as a user facility for nuclear and particle physics, with an internal gas target at moderate beam currents of 1-10 mA.

Examples for future ERLs under preparation are:

- PERLE@Orsay in France (superconducting, multi-turn) [16]
- electron cooler ERL for EIC at BNL in USA (superconducting, single or multi-turn) [17]
- LHeC at CERN in Switzerland and France (superconducting, multi-turn) [18]

PERLE will be a test facility for a future high-energy lepton-hadron collider LHeC, or FCC-eh, that would collide a hadron beam circulating in the LHC or FCC-hh, respectively, with electrons provided by an ERL. The PERLE test facility is planned to be installed at IJClab in Orsay. It should operate in the 10 MW beam power regime. PERLE is designed as a compact double-sided multi pass ERL with two SRF linacs. It shall serve as test bed for novel beam dynamics phenomena, inform the development of optimized technologies, and help define the technical choices for future projects, like the Large Hadron Electron Collider (LHeC). The LHeC proposal would be validated by the successful

operation of a multi-turn SRF ERL with high average beam current. Such a validation is needed before proceeding with the design and construction of the LHeC ERL, which aims at operating in the GW beam power regime. The ERLs serving as electron coolers for hadron beams need beam energies in the 100 MeV range, but very high beam current of ~100 mA; they are challenging in terms of the small energy spread and long bunch length required for efficient cooling.

In summary, the existing and planned facilities are setting the path to even bigger future machines. The only planned ERL user facility so far will be MESA at Mainz, running at a moderate beam power. All others are test facilities mainly designed for testing and extending the limits of the ERL concept. In the near future, the safe operation of multi MW beams in multi-turn settings need to be proven in order to pave the way towards even larger ERL machines, such as LHeC or ERL based light sources.

2.2 ERL BEAM DYNAMICS AND INSTRUMENTATION

The ERL architecture is mainly determined by the longitudinal beam dynamics requirements, as accelerating and decelerating bunches need a 180° spacing in terms of the RF wavelength of the accelerating cavities. The transverse design follows the longitudinal settings [19]. Different ERL applications demand different beam properties. For FELs one desires a high peak current. Nuclear and particle-physics applications do not need such a high peak current, but instead they require a small relative energy spread. Finally, electron cooling applications call for long bunches and an extremely small energy spread. Both challenges, high peak current and small energy spread, can be addressed by using a lattice with a tailored finite momentum compaction factor, or by introducing harmonic RF systems. Using finite momentum compaction, can render the decelerating process rather complicated as in the decelerating path the sign of the slope of the RF wave changes while the momentum compaction stays the same and, therefore, the beam quality is constantly decreasing [20]. This aspect needs to be considered carefully; otherwise a large fraction of the beam could be lost before reaching the beam dump [21].

2.2.1 General ERL Layout

In any ERL, the beams of different energy, corresponding to different passes, at least share the same beamline elements along the linac axis. For the arcs different approaches are considered. The classic way is to use individual arcs for each energy, so that accelerating and decelerating bunches of (nearly) the same energy are sharing the same arcs, meaning that always two beams are overlaid in each arc. A different approach is the use of fixed-field alternating gradient (FFA) lattices, where all bunches over a wide energy range can be transported through the same arc. This concept is used at CBETA, where eight beams of four different energies share the same arc and the same beam pipe [12]. On the other hand, layouts with completely separated beamlines are possible as well, when a double-sided ERL design with two linacs is pursued. Here, the injection of the decelerating beam needs to be done into the second linac resulting in a separation of accelerating and decelerating beams [22] which is useful for beam control and diagnostics on the one hand, but on the other hand comes along with the need for installing twice the number of arc beamlines. Figure 1 illustrates the difference between the FFA design with one arc and the design with separated beamlines for each energy.

Fig. 1 Two design approaches for a multi-turn ERL. Left side: individual return arcs by injecting the decelerated beam into the second linac of a double-sided layout [22]. Right side: one FFAG recirculation arc for all beam energies as realized at CBETA [12].

The separated design gives full control of each individual beam and allows shaping the momentum compaction and a focusing matched to the experimental and stability needs. The disadvantage is clearly given by the additional costs for installation and powering of the enlarged number of magnets. The FFAG design is very cost effective and, when realized with permanent magnets, like at CBETA, superior in terms of installation and operating costs. The trade-off is the lower flexibility of the optics and the issue of many overlying beams, which complicates beam diagnostics and beam control. For future ERLs, the operational experience of CBETA and other multi-turn ERLs need to be compared, in order to define the best solutions for future projects, e.g., the optimum LHeC configuration.

2.2.2 Collective effects

For the electron beams in ERLs, collective effects come along with the high intensity and, therefore, high bunch charge of such accelerators. In the past, beam break-up (BBU) has been investigated a lot, as it can clearly limit the achievable beam current in ERLs [23]. But today, BBU is no longer recognized as a major problem anymore, since dedicated simulation codes [24] and HOM damped SRF cavities as well as adapted optics have all been developed as mitigation measures. The main issues presently under investigation by the community are coherent synchrotron radiation (CSR) and microbunching effects, which appear to be the main challenges for future machines and shall be investigated further in the future. The existing simulation codes need to be extended e.g. by Vlasov-based models [19]. Another focus of instability research will be on the development and mitigation of beam halo, which can aggravate collective effects, increase beam losses, degrade energy efficiency, and may even cause damage to the accelerator components. Halos can result from beam-target interaction at the experiment or from space charge and beam filamentation, in particular, in the low energy beam transport. Efficient collimation strategies are already under investigation [25,26], and this effort should clearly be continued.

2.2.3 Beam diagnostics and instrumentation

The high beam intensities and the fact, that multiple beams of different energies can be present in the same beam pipe at (almost) the same time implies new challenges for the beam diagnostics. For beam commissioning on the other hand one works with low beam intensities. For that reason, development of destructive and non-destructive beam diagnostics with a wide dynamic range is the focus of the worldwide R&D effort and needs to be pursued. Synergies with other accelerator communities are evident.

2.3 ELECTRON SOURCES AND INJECTORS

The challenges for ERL photocathodes and injectors are linked to the demand for high beam current with a high duty cycle up to continuous wave operation. Thermionic dc guns can deliver the 100 mA required for coolers or high current ERLs, but if polarized beams or high time resolution are needed one has to go for photocathodes or RF guns, respectively [27]. For photocathodes, the cathode lifetime constitutes a major issue as quantum efficiency drops with extracted current, both from heating of the cathodes by the laser system and from ion back-bombardment on the cathodes. This results in lifetimes of a few days only, for the current materials of choice (alkali antimonides), requiring constant production or refreshment of cathodes, during longer runs of operation. The profile of the laser also leads to halo creation, with repercussions on the beam dynamics (see last section). Both these effects are aggravated if spin polarization is also needed. So far GaAs superlattices remain the only option for generating polarized beams. The corresponding cathodes are characterized not only by a poor charge lifetime, but also by significant longitudinal and transverse beam-halo tails due to the emission process. One possible method to increase the charge lifetime of polarized injectors could be efficient cathode cooling, which, though challenging, appears promising.

In summary, various research on cathodes and SRF injectors is underway, and this needs to be continued in order to achieve reliable electron sources for present and future ERL projects. Table 1 shows an overview of gun research presented at the 2019 ERL workshop. The so far best performing SRF gun provides 10 nC of bunch charge at a reasonable lifetime [28].

	HZDR	PKU	BNL	KEK	Novosibirsk	HZB	Jlab (magnetized)
Status	In operation	In operation	In operation	In operation	R&D	R&D	R&D
Gun energy [MeV]	4	4	1.3	0.5	0.3	1.5-2.3	0.3
Cathode material	Mg(Cs ₂ Te)	Cs ₂ Te	KCsSb	GaAs	Thermionic	KCsSb	KCsSb
Bunch charge [pC]	300	50	10,000	60	2,000	100	700
Ave. current [mA]	0.03(1)	1	0.12	1	102	/	28
Peak current [A]	100	9	1.5 @600pC	13	3/5		9.3
Lifetime	1 year	3 weeks	1-2 months	10 hrs?	Year ?	/	90 hrs
Nor. Emittance[um]	13	1.5	0.57@600pC	0.8/1.9	8	<0.5	<2 26(drift)

Table. 1 Overview of gun research as presented at the ERL workshop 2019 [27].

2.4 SUPERCONDUCTING RF

In ERLs the SRF systems are running at moderate accelerating gradients, but in cw operation sometimes with extremely high loaded quality values. The high Q value together with the need to correct beam phasing errors poses a challenge for the RF systems. The operation in cw mode makes the unloaded quality factor Q_0 of the accelerating cavities an important issue for matching the cryogenic capacities of a given facility. Finally, the efficient damping of unwanted higher order modes (HOMs) is crucial in ERLs, to maintain the stability of the RF system and to mitigate BBU.

These three main research topics have been identified in WG4 of ERL 2019 [29], and are further discussed in the following subsections.

2.4.1 High loaded Q cavity operation

As ERLs operate with low to zero beam loading (beam loading of accelerating and decelerating beams cancel out in an efficient recovery operation, despite having a lot of beam current passing through the cavities), SRF linacs can be operated at quite high loaded Q-factors (up to 10^8), which on the other hand makes these cavities very sensitive to microphonics. The microphonics need to be controlled passively and actively. Passive control of mechanical vibrations includes absorbing supports of all mechanical components in the module like mounting frames, waveguide components, vacuum and water pumps, cryogenic transfer lines and compressor systems. The mechanical eigenmodes of all components of the cryomodule need to be identified and mitigated if harmful. In addition, cryogenic instabilities may be major microphonics drivers, causing pressure waves in the helium systems [30]. Active microphonics control can be accomplished through the LLRF system and, in particular, by adding fast tuners and fast feedback systems. Recent advances in ferroelectric ceramics have opened up new possibilities for fast reactive tuners in SRF cavity applications [31].

2.4.2 HOMs, HOM damping and high current operation

Extracting HOM power efficiently from SRF cavities, without introducing potential breakdown weaknesses, is a significant challenge for high current ERL linacs [29]. HOMs are connected to BBU instability and need to be damped according to the envisaged beam current. While TESLA/XFEL type resonators extract HOMs using antennas [32], which can be a bottleneck for high current operation [33], modern ERL modules accomplish the HOM extraction with the help of waveguides or beamline absorbers based on newly developed broadband ceramic and ferrite absorbing materials [34]. HOM load solutions at 1.3 GHz and 1.5 GHz [34] are existing, and are already serving most of the actual ERL projects. For future high-current operation more operational experience will be necessary to benchmark the newly developed systems. Therefore, operating the few existing ERLs at high beam current is a crucial ingredient of future research on this topic.

2.4.3 High Q_0 cavity performance

ERL cavities are operated in cw at moderate accelerating gradient. Due to the continuous operation the unloaded quality factor of the cavities is an important issue, as cryogenic losses are directly connected to that number. At most actual ERLs, which are compact machines, a degradation of cavity performance during operation has been observed [35]. The fact that the performance degrades over time probably indicates a slow contamination from the surrounding warm beam line elements. Future ERL projects like PERLE or LHeC will work with a lower resonance frequency of 801.56 MHz compared to the 1.3 or 1.5 GHz of most existing projects. This will relax the Q_0 issue a little, thanks to the decreasing BCS resistance. Nevertheless, also for these machines, cleanliness requirements even for the warm parts should be as strict as for the cold parts in order to protect the cavities against contamination. Future research could focus on the use of new cavity treatments like nitrogen doping [36], which allows for extremely high-quality factors at medium accelerating gradient, as envisaged for ERLs. Whereas, so far, none of the actual projects is considering the use of this technology, it can be an interesting path towards highly-efficient SRF operation at future ERLs.

2.5 ERL APPLICATIONS

At the beginning of the 21st century the most likely application of larger ERL facilities had been thought to be photon sources using FELs or the production of diffraction-limited synchrotron radiation [37]. Here, the good beam quality of ERLs, in particular, the much smaller transverse emittance compared with storage rings, promised significant improvements in the light quality. For that reason, many design studies from that period aimed at the implementation of a 4th generation light source based on ERL technology. Due to great improvements in storage-ring optics since then, the by now the experimental focus has shifted to other applications of ERLs. Current projects are going to use the unique ERL beam for particle-physics electron-scattering experiments (MESA), searches for dark matter (MESA, CBETA), lithography (cERL), Compton-backscattered photon generation (S-DALINAC) or studies and beam tests paving the way towards proposed larger ERLs for electron-hadron colliders (CBETA, PERLE). In the future, the ERL technology could be used in colliding-beam experiments (LHeC, in EICs like eRHIC – if later upgraded with a collider ERL [38] – MEIC [39], and even for a high-energy highest-luminosity electron-positron collider Higgs and top factory FCC-ee-ERL [40]), or as high-energy electron coolers for hadron storage rings [17]. For the future colliders, beam power in the GW range needs to be achieved. Other possible applications could be ERLs in industry, e.g. as drivers of EUV-FELs for lithography [41]. As the field of research progresses, ERL applications in research and industry should be developed and exploited [42].

3. Summary and Outlook

At present, the research field of ERLs is extremely vibrant and dynamic, with several projects in operation, and a few others on the way to completion. A major milestone has recently been achieved with the operation of the first SRF multi-turn ERL based on FFA return arcs. Accelerator research for ERLs addresses topics similar to those pursued by other accelerator communities, such as SRF, beam dynamics, injectors and control systems. Therefore, a close connection and collaboration between different accelerator science communities is existing and should be continued, if not further enhanced. The research specific to ERLs should be based on pushing the existing and near-future facilities to their maximum stable beam current, thereby gaining even more operational experience. The latter will define the necessary technological steps for constructing future multi MW facilities. Finally, an established high-current multi-turn ERL technology will provide a pathway to future highly energy-efficient accelerators.

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